

Ligations from homocysteine isopeptide via 6-membered cyclic transition states[†]

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Abstract : Efficient synthesis of *S*-acyl homocysteine allow chemical ligation (*S*-acyl to *N*-acyl transfer) via 6-membered cyclic transition state. The results represent the first example of successful isopeptide ligation starting from *S*-acyl homocysteine.

Keywords : Homocysteine isopeptide, ligation, S to N-acyl migration, microwave.

Introduction

Synthetic methods for peptides are of great interest : native chemical ligation (NCL) is a widely used chemoselective technique to synthesize large peptides involving *S*-acylation by a peptidethioester of the *N*-terminal cysteine residue of another peptide followed by *S*→*N* acyl migration to form a native amide linkage^{1,2}. Recent significant achievements of NCL include the total chemical synthesis of both post-translationally modified and unmodified proteins², segmental isotopic labeling of proteins for NMR studies^{3,4} and the formation of peptide conjugates with macromolecules such as peptide nucleic acids^{5,6} and DNA^{6,7}. NCL has been particularly useful for assembling proteins that can probe biomolecular processes *in vitro*^{2,8,9} and *in vivo*¹⁰⁻¹².

NCL has been extensively studied in peptidic compounds bearing a cysteine residue at the *N*-terminus¹³. Modified cysteine scaffolds have also been utilized for the syntheses of novel peptides and proteins¹⁴⁻¹⁷ and for surface immobilization¹⁸. For instance, *N*-acyl cysteines have found utility as photoactivatable analogues of glutathione¹⁹ and for the synthesis of oxytocin-like peptides²⁰.

Haase and co-workers showed that an internal cysteine with glycine or alanine as the *N*-terminal residue enhanced the rate of NCL ligation. The ligation rate de-

pends on the ring size formed during the *S*→*N* acyl transfer²¹. Wong and co-workers reported that *N*-terminal glycine favors second-generation sugar-assisted ligation in cysteine-containing and cysteine-free glycopeptides over sterically encumbered L-amino acids like valine, leucine, isoleucine and proline²². According to a generally accepted notion, the subsequent acyl shift should proceed via entropically favored 5- and 6-membered ring intermediates in order to achieve useful rates.

S-Acyl peptides have helped elucidate biophysical, structural and other properties of *S*-acylated proteins of mammalian cells²³. While peptides lacking free hydroxyl or amino groups can be efficiently *S*-acylated by acyl chlorides²⁴, specific *S*-acylation of cysteine-containing peptides has remained a synthetic challenge, given the lability of the thioester bond²³. We demonstrated previously that peptide coupling of *N*-(Pg- α -aminoacyl)benzotriazoles with unprotected amino acids in MeCN-H₂O occurs with preservation of chirality²⁵. Our group has studied the feasibility of chemical ligation of *S*-acylated cysteine peptides via 5-, 8-14 and 17-19-membered cyclic transition states, leading to the corresponding native di-, tetra-, penta- and hexapeptides without the use of auxiliaries²⁶⁻²⁹. We found that 8-membered transition states are clearly disfavored whereas the 9-14 and 17-19-membered transition

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

states are relatively favored for ligations in *S*-acyl isopeptides containing terminal cysteine residues²⁹.

We now report the microwave-assisted chemical ligations (1 h, 50 °C) of *S*-acyl isopeptide containing a homocysteine unit to form native peptides via a 6-membered transition state without the use of auxiliaries.

Results and discussion

Preparation of (*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)homocysteine (**4**) :

The *N*-Boc protection of 4,4'-disulfanediylbis(2-aminobutanoic acid) **1** was achieved following a previously reported method (Scheme 1)³⁰, affording compound **3** in 98% yield. Compound **3** was then treated with PBU₃ in an aqueous methanol mixture to afford (*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)homocysteine (**4**) in 48% yields.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of (*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)homocysteine **4**.

Preparation of the mono-isodipeptide (**7**) :

(*tert*-Butoxycarbonyl)homocysteine **4** was *S*-acylated with Cbz-L-Ala-Bt **5** (prepared by our reported procedure)²⁵ in the presence of KHCO₃ to provide Boc-protected mono-isodipeptide **6** which, after deprotection by dioxane-HCl (g), yielded the mono-isotetrapeptide **7** in 88% yield (Scheme 2).

Study of *S*→*N* acyl migration via a 6-membered cyclic transition state :

Chemical ligation via a 6-membered cyclic transition state was investigated by subjecting mono-isodipeptide **7**

to microwave (MW) irradiation at 50 °C, 50 W irradiation power for 1 h in 1 *M* NaH₂PO₄/Na₂HPO₄ phosphate buffer to maintain pH 7.3²⁷. The reaction was allowed to cool to room temperature, MeCN was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was acidified with 2 *N* HCl to pH 1. The mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 20 mL), the combined organic extracts were dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The ligation mixture was weighed and then a solution in methanol was analyzed by HPLC-HRMS.

HPLC-HRMS (ESI) analysis of the ligated mixture showed the expected migration product **8** (rt 28.846, *m/z* 341.1185) together with intermolecular transacylation product **9** (rt 36.264, *m/z* 546.1923) and the disulfide dimer of the expected ligated product **10** (rt 36.377, *m/z*

679.2122). It is well known³¹ that small cysteine-containing peptides are easily dimerized oxidatively in solution when exposed to air in the absence of a reducing agent.

HPLC-HRMS, via (+) ESI-MS, confirmed that the ligated product **8** (rt 28.846, *m/z* 341.1185) and starting mono-isohexapeptide **7** (rt 22.944, *m/z* 341.1182) produced different MS patterns. The relative abundance of the crude ligated mixture as analyzed by analytical HPLC is shown in Table 1. The result indicates the formation of ligated products (**8**+**10**) with 98% relative abundance,

Scheme 2. Synthesis of monoisodi-peptide 7.

Scheme 3. Chemical ligation reaction of monoisodi-peptide 7.

which shows that $S \rightarrow N$ acyl group migration via a 6-membered transition state is preferred over intermolecular acylation. Thus, acyl migration via a 6-membered cyclic transition state is feasible and may afford a promi-

sing approach for the synthesis of native peptide analog-containing homocysteine (Table 1).

This result is consistent with our previous work in which we reported similar $S \rightarrow N$ acyl migration by an

Table 1. Chemical ligation of *S*-acyl isodipeptide

React	Cyclic TS size	Crude yield (%)	Relative amounts of each product (%) ^{a,b,c}				Product characterization by HPLC-MS					
			R	LM	LD	TA	Ligated peptide monomer (LM)		Ligated peptide dimer (LD)		Transacylation product (TA)	
							LM	[M+H] ⁺ found	LD	[M+H] ⁺	TA	[M+H] ⁺
7	6	85	0	45.44	50.35	4.20	8	341.1185	10	679.2122	9	546.1923

^aDetermined by HPLC-HRMS semiquantitative. The area of ion-peak resulting from the sum of the intensities of the [M+H]⁺ and [M+Na]⁺ ions of each compound was integrated; ^bR = recovered reactant, LM = ligation monomer, LD = ligation dimer, TA = transacylation; ^camounts are corrected for LD = 2 mmol, LM = 1 mmol.

intramolecular mechanism^{26–29}, supported by competitive experiments²⁹ and computational arguments³².

Conclusion

In conclusion, our methodology affords the synthesis of a homocysteine-containing isopeptide. We studied acyl migration from *S* to the *N*-terminus of NH₂ group under microwave-irradiation and found the intramolecular acyl transfer through 6-TS appeared to be favored. Our microwave-assisted isopeptide ligation offers the following advantages : (i) short reaction times (1 h) at moderate temperature (50 °C), (ii) chemical ligation from cysteine analog and (iii) avoidance of ligation auxiliaries. In contrast to the classical native chemical ligation approach, our methodology allows the isolation of *S*-acyl peptide intermediates, which might be useful in several synthetic and biological applications³³.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a capillary point apparatus equipped with a digital thermometer. NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆ on Mercury NMR spectrometers operating at 300 MHz for ¹H (with TMS as an internal standard) and 75 MHz for ¹³C. Microwave-assisted reaction was carried out with a single mode cavity Discover Microwave Synthesizer (CEM Corporation, NC). The reaction mixtures were transferred into a 10 mL glass pressure microwave tube equipped with a magnetic stir bar. The tube was closed with a silicon septum and the reaction mixture was subjected to microwave irradiation (Discover mode; run time : 60 s; PowerMax-cooling mode). HPLC-HRMS analyses were performed on reverse phase gradient using Agilent (Santa Clara, CA) 1200 series binary pump (G1312B), waters XTerra MS C18 (3.5 μm; 2.1 × 150 mm) + Phenomenex C18 security guard column (2 × 4 mm) using 0.2% ace-

tic acid in H₂O/methanol as mobile phases; wavelength = 254 nm; and mass spectrometry was done with 6220 Agilent (Santa Clara, CA) TOF in electrospray ionization (ESI) mode with positive and negative ESI-MS method in both Profile and Centroid modes.

4, 4'-Disulfanediybis(2-((tert-butoxycarbonyl)-amino)butanoic acid) (3) :

To a solution of L-homocysteine **1** (1.34 g, 5.0 mmol) in 10% sodium carbonate solution (30 mL) and dioxane (25 mL) cooled in an ice bath was added di-*t*-butyl dicarbonate (2.4 g, 11.1 mmol). The mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred overnight. The solution was adjusted to pH 4 with 10% citric acid and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 20 mL). The organic layers were combined, washed with brine (2 × 10 mL), dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated to give compound **3** as a white solid (98%); m.p. 153–155 °C (lit. m.p. 152–154 °C)³⁰; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.13 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 4.09–3.87 (2H, m), 2.84–2.62 (4H, m), 2.15–1.78 (4H, m), 1.50–1.25 (18H, s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 173.7, 155.6, 78.2, 66.4, 52.2, 34.2, 30.4, 28.2.

(tert-Butoxycarbonyl)homocysteine (4) :

Compound **3** (0.5 g, 1.07 mmol) was treated with PBu₃ (0.32 g, 1.60 mmol) in CH₃OH : H₂O (9 : 1 mL) for 2 h at room temperature. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was concentrated under vacuum and the residue was diluted with ethyl acetate (15 mL). The solution was dried over MgSO₄ and then evaporated to obtain compound **4** as white solid (84%); m.p. 86–87 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 11.27 (1H, s), 4.58–4.23 (1H, m), 2.78–2.44 (2H, m), 2.29–1.89 (2H, m), 1.45 (9H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 176.1, 155.8, 80.4, 52.3, 36.9, 28.3, 20.8.

Panda *et al.* : Ligation from homocysteine isopeptide via 6-membered cyclic transition state*S*-((*N*-Benzyloxycarbonyl)-*L*-alanyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)homocysteine (**6**) :

A mixture of Boc-Hcys-OH (0.5 g, 2.12 mmol) and KHCO₃ (0.44 g, 3.18 mmol) in CH₃CN : H₂O (15 : 5 mL) was stirred at 20 °C for 30 min. After the formation of a clear solution, Z-*L*-Ala-Bt (0.69 g, 2.12 mmol) was added slowly. The solution was left to stir at room temperature for 3 h until completion (monitored by TLC). Upon completion, CH₃CN was removed under reduced pressure and ethyl acetate (30 mL) was added. The solution was washed with HCl (1 *N*, 3 × 10 mL), water (1 × 10 mL) and brine (1 × 10 mL) then dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to yield the desired product as colorless oil (79%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.33 (5H, br s), 7.15 (2H, br s), 5.63–5.46 (1H, m), 5.41–5.25 (1H, m), 5.22–5.03 (2H, m), 4.54–4.22 (2H, m), 3.01–2.83 (2H, m), 2.22–1.80 (2H, m), 1.55 (9H, s), 1.37 (3H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 175.5, 155.9, 136.2, 128.7, 128.5, 128.3, 126.3, 80.6, 67.5, 57.0, 52.7, 32.3, 28.5, 25.0, 18.8. HRMS Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₈N₂O₇S [M-H]⁺ 439.1544; Found 439.1563.

3-((*N*-Benzyloxy)carbonyl)-*L*-alanylthio)-*l*-carboxypropan-*l*-ammonium chloride (**7**) :

The Boc-protected mono-isodipeptide **6** (0.2 g, 0.45 mmol) was stirred in dioxane-HCl (g) (5 mL) for 1 h. Dioxane was evaporated under reduced pressure, and the residue was treated with diethyl ether. The resulted turbid solution was kept at –5 °C overnight. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with diethyl ether to yield the desired hydrochloride salt as white solid (88%); m.p. 172–174 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 8.61 (2H, br s), 8.12 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 7.34 (5H, br s), 5.17–4.95 (2H, s), 3.94–3.72 (1H, m), 3.11–2.74 (2H, m), 2.13–1.88 (2H, m), 1.25 (3H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.4 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 202.3, 170.3, 155.8, 136.8, 128.4, 127.9, 127.8, 65.7, 56.7, 51.5, 40.3, 40.1, 39.8, 39.5, 39.2, 39.0, 38.7, 30.1, 23.9, 17.3. HRMS Calcd. for C₁₅H₂₀N₂O₅S [M+H]⁺ 341.1149; Found 341.1148.

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